

Quantum Bound Density and Time Through Impulse

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A classical bound system may be said to have a spatial density proportional to the amount of time dt a particle spends in a constant dx region i.e. $C/v(x)$ (1) We stress that in this scenario there is a well defined and constant dx so that “ dt ” may be linked to velocity $v(x)$. We also note that there is no spatial representation of action-reaction here even though this exists in Newton’s theory.

In a classical Maxwell-Boltzmann gas there are many particles which each act dynamically according to $.5mv^2 + V(x) = E$ (where v and E are particular to the particle when it is not colliding). At the same time there is a spatial density which “represents” macroscopic static chunks of matter which are balanced through pressure differences ($P = \text{spatial density}(x) RT$) and $-dV/dx$ density where $V(x)$ is the potential. From the pressure equation, T is proportional to energy which in turn is proportional to RMS speed squared. RMS speed may then be linked to a dt if a fixed dx is understood. In the classical statistical case, however, spatial density is directly linked to the number of particles in a region. Time enters in the pressure expression through a term proportional to the average kinetic energy i.e. pv where p is like an impulse and v a flux.

What happens in a single particle quantum bound state? In a sense it is like a classical bound state as the equation: $p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m + V(x) = E_n$ holds for any energy level. Can one then take $v_{rms}(x)$, choose a fixed dx and argue that spatial density should be equal to dt or $C/v_{rms}(x)$? We argue that one cannot due to the lack of defined “ dx ” quantity. Why is dx problematic to define? We argue that it is because quantum mechanics is based on action-reaction x -probability distributions linked to impulse. For example, $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle captures only p or impulse (not velocity) and $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are its action-reaction regions. These lead ultimately to a density is given by the well-known $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, although kinetic energy with $pp/2m = .5pv^2$ is used to find $W(x)$ as well. $W^*(x)W(x)$ has crests and troughs similar to $\cos(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$, except that these now have varying heights and widths.

We try to argue that even though each x point maps to a different $KE_{ave}(x)$, the hump physically represents action-reaction in the system (just as the humps in $\cos(px)$ do except for a single p) while $KE(x)$ represents an average of p ’s. This action-reaction is linked with impulses. In general, if one takes d/dx of the time-independent Schrodinger equation one finds an average impulse term, $-dV/dx$ and $KE(x) dW/dx / W$ where $dW/dx / W$ is the average impulse. At peaks, $dW/dx = 0$ and so an average force through time*impulse term balances $-dV/dx = \text{Newtonian force}$. These peaks are also associated with $W^*(x \text{ at peak})W(x \text{ at peak})$ which is the spatial density. We interpret this as representing the average time the single particle spends near x at peak. This value, however, follows from ideas of impulse and not from speed as there is no well defined dx even though there is a well defined $v_{rms}(x)$. Thus the ratio of $W^*(x)W(x)$ at two peaks is not the inverse of the ratio of $v_{rms}(x)$ except apparently when the energy level n becomes very high.

We investigate these ideas.

Classical Spatial Bound Density

In (1) it is stated that a classical bound system: $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ has different $dt(x)$ at each constant dx and so $dt(x)$ is proportional to a spatial density. Thus the classical bound spatial density is:

$C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ = velocity and C is a normalization constant ((1))

As an example, consider a particle bound in a region of length L with constant velocity v . At first it might seem that spatial density depends on velocity, but one calculates a spatial density which means that time is “frozen” out and one only wants a probability to be at each dx . Thus all constant velocities with L lead to the same density namely:

$\text{density}(x) dx = dx/L$ ((2))

How can this be? A slow particle spends more time in dx than a fast one, but the fast one has a larger frequency. Thus frequency * dt is constant i.e.

Frequency = v/L and time spent in dx is proportional to $1/v$ so the product is independent of v .

For a constant velocity, $C=v/L$ which is the frequency.

We stress this point because for a quantum free particle $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ regardless of p and hence v if m (mass) is known. Even if spatial density is constant, there is still a sense of time in the problem due to $\exp(-i pp^2/m t)$ which depends on both p and m . Thus the spatial density may be the same for any $\exp(ipx)$, but the average kinetic energy $pp/2m$ carries a sense of time through flux. For a bound system, however, this sense of time is carried by $\exp(-i E_n t)$ where E_n is the total energy which includes both kinetic and potential energy.

Before considering the single particle quantum bound state, we note that according to Newtonian mechanics there should be action-reaction. We argue that this should lead to a spatial distribution in x due to the force acting, but that this does not appear in classical mechanics. It does, however, appear in quantum mechanics, we argue. In fact, we have suggested in previous notes that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ from the two dimensional $\exp(ipx)$ capture the action reaction present in a free particle. The action-reaction between the two distributions may be seen through the positive and negative slopes of both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. This implies peak points with zero slope and hence crests/troughs. As a result, the physical spatial presence of action-reaction leads to a density of its own and we argue that this is critical in a quantum bound system. Furthermore, given that spatial density may be interpreted as the time spent near x , then the action-reaction scheme is responsible for the time intervals associated with peaks. For a free particle, $\cos(px)$ peaks all have the same height of 1 so the time intervals are the same. For the bound state, matters differ.

Lorentz Invariant $-Et+px$

We consider the Lorentz invariant $A=-Et+px$ and note that x and t are general variables. "P" is specific to an impulse which means there are sets of m_0, v which yield the same p . Thus considering $\exp(ipx)$ only, which is the eigenfunction of $-i\partial/\partial x$ where $\partial A/\partial x = p$, leads to a picture of impulses only. $E=pp/2m$ (non relativistically) requires two pieces of information p and m_0 . In the nonrelativistic case, one sees that it carries knowledge of the impulse and velocity (i.e. flux) which in a sense gives information about time because the impulse $\int F dt$ contains dt and is linked to the speed of the particle. Thus the probability distributions $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ associated with $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. an impulse, may influence the average kinetic energy (linked to velocity) as it is subjected to the probability associated with action/reaction. This becomes apparent in the quantum single particle bound state considered in the next section.

Single Particle Bound State

What seems to be happening in a single particle bound state? For a free particle, $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ and both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ have peaks and troughs representing action/reaction even though each x point maps to p and $pp/2m$. On average the particle travels as $x=p/m t$, but within a peak there is probability, not a deterministic $x(t)$ relation.

In a bound state, the wavelength associated with p cannot be ignored because it is of the length of the system and physically represents the action-reaction region. This leads to uncertainty in position within the system and if one considers the external average $x=p/m t$, it is possible that a particle moving to the right with p is either somewhere within a wavelength from the "turning point" or has already turned. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ terms must be combined. Furthermore other p 's may be included leading to the ensemble:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

From ((3)) one sees that the crest regions are key and represent the physical action/reaction features of the system which do not appear in Newtonian mechanics, although it is stated that action-reaction is present. The idea of action-reaction is so important we argue that ((3)) leads to a system of crests and troughs which physically represent new action reaction regions i.e. the average ((3)) leads to an action-reaction scheme with different average $KE(x)$ values and hence different $v_{rms}(x)$ values at each x . Thus, unlike $\cos(px)$ the action-reaction region is no longer associated with a single p or $pp/2m$. Nevertheless, it is still key and does not disappear in the so-called classical limit i.e. the high n limit, it just becomes very small.

The action-reaction form is important and leads to crests/troughs because one has positive and negative slopes of $W(x)$. There must then be peak points with $dW/dx = 0$ and these may vary with height. We note that:

$$dW/dx / W = \text{average impulse} \quad \text{so at peak points there is no average impulse} \quad ((4))$$

If peak points may have different heights, then the densities $W^*(x)W(x)$ at these points differ. We suggest that this means the particle spends different amounts of time around different peaks.

What does this mean in terms of $v_{rms}(x)$? In the classical bound system the density at dx is due strictly to dt associated with $v=dx/dt$ with dx being constant. In the quantum bound state, however, it is the action-reaction crest which is key and this is not found in the classical bound picture even though $.5mv_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x) + V(x) = E_n$ holds in both.

One may fix the $a(p)$'s in ((3)) through:

$$\left\{ \sum_{\text{over } p} \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((5))$$

{To see the relationship with ((4)) more clearly, one may take d/dx of ((5)) i.e.

$$\left\{ \sum_{\text{over } p} \frac{pp}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) = \frac{dW/dx}{W} - \frac{dV/dx}{dx} \quad ((5b))$$

If $dW/dx = 0$, then the term on the LHS represents, we argue, $\frac{p^2}{2m} p$ or $1/\text{time} * \text{impulse}$ where time is taken from $\exp(-i \frac{p^2}{2m} t)$. This impulse based force average equals Newtonian force $-dV/dx$ at peak points.. The quantum feature is the presence of a wavelength associated with these peaks describing the action-reaction region. Thus the peak points are not "classical" unless the "wavelength" region is so small as to constitute all or part of a constant tiny dx length.}

One may associate the first term of ((5)) with $KE_{ave}(x)$ and compute $v_{rms}(x)$. This, however, cannot be linked directly to time because there is no physical dx in the system, only a mathematical one. This is due to the action-reaction region just as in the case of $\cos(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$. Within a wavelength one cannot assume $x=p/m t$ where $p=\text{constant}$ because one has an x -probability distribution. Thus the idea of dt representing density within a crest does not hold for a free particle.

We argue that the same scenario holds for a single bound particle. $v_{rms}(x)$ holds on average, but not in any strict sense within a crest of a bound system. Thus one cannot assign a dt proportional to $1/v_{rms}(x)$ to a peak within a bound system. Rather one must assign a time associated with $W^*(x)W(x)$ which is linked to both the average kinetic energy (linked to $V(x)$ and E_n) and the various action-reaction crests associated with $\cos(px)$'s of the various p 's in ((3)).

Thus there is a sense of time, even in a quantum bound state based on the time-independent Schrodinger equation. This is because this equation makes use of average kinetic energy which contains velocity which in turn is linked to average time. It is, however, the "new" crest/trough system which is used to create the energy conservation equation $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$, while retaining $\cos(px)$ action/reaction regions which ultimately leads to a spatial density which defines "time in the system. This differs then from both the classical bound particle sense of time and that in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas.

High Energy Case

We argued that a key idea in a single particle bound state is that of action-reaction regions i.e. crests/troughs. These are linked with variable "wavelengths" which represent significant

proportions of the region in which the particle is mostly found (i.e. within a region comparable to one bound by the classical turning points). As the energy level, however, increases to a very high level, these "wavelengths" become small compared to this length. In such a case, a crest may be seen to correspond to a dx . One might even make constant dx 's with more than one crest within each. These crests within the same dx would have roughly the same height because their wavelengths are so small. In such a case, $v_{rms}(x)=dx/dt$ may be linked with a physical dx region (which still contains the physical action-reaction) and so dt would be a measure of probability. $W^*(x)W(x)$, however, still remains a measure of probability as well and so at peak points it should be proportional to dt or $1/v_{rms}(x)$, a relationship used in (1).

References

1. Majernik, Vladimir; Richterek, Lukas (1997-12-01). "[Entropic uncertainty relations for the infinite well](#)". J. Phys. A. 30 (4): L49. [Bibcode:1997JPhA...30L..49M](#). [doi:10.1088/0305-4470/30/4/002](#)